

SOCIAL-ECONOMIC IMPACT ANALYSIS OF ZAINUDDIN ABDUL MAJID AIRPORT DEVELOPMENT FOR HEADS OF FAMILIES IN TANAK AWU VILLAGE, CENTRAL LOMBOK REGENCY

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Abstract: *The purpose of this study was to determine the social impact of the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport on heads of families in Tanak Awu Village and the economic impact of the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport on heads of families in Tanak Awu Village. This study used a qualitative method involving 16 heads of families in Tanak Awu Hamlet as research informants. Data were collected through interviews and analyzed using the Miles and Huberman qualitative data analysis model, which includes data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results indicate that the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid International Airport has had significant social and economic impacts on heads of families in Tanak Awu Village, Central Lombok Regency. From a social perspective, the airport's construction has encouraged a shift in the community's mindset, making it more open and future-oriented, raising awareness of the importance of education, and influencing people's behavior to become more active in various economic and social activities. Cultural change has also occurred selectively, with the community maintaining local customs and traditions while adapting to modern developments. Economically, the airport's presence has contributed to increased income and community well-being through increased business and employment opportunities, as well as a shift in livelihoods from the agricultural sector to the service and trade sectors. However, the utilization of these economic opportunities has not been fully equitable, as it is still influenced by education levels, skills, and labor competition. Overall, the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Madjid Airport has had a positive impact on social transformation and improving the economic conditions of the Tanak Awu Village community.*

Keywords: *Socio-economic impact, head of household, Zainuddin Abdul Madjid Airport.*

Introduction

Development is a process of planned change aimed at improving the quality of life of the community through various aspects, including economic, social, cultural, political, and infrastructure. The goal of development is not only oriented towards economic growth but also towards improving the welfare of the community evenly across all regions (Anggara, 2016). In its implementation, development requires adequate infrastructure support because infrastructure plays a crucial role in encouraging mobility, connectivity, and economic activity. The availability of good transportation infrastructure can accelerate economic growth and support the development of a region (Dumatubun, 2024). One of the infrastructures that plays a strategic role in regional development is the airport. Airports serve as a means of transportation connecting one region to another, while also driving economic growth through increased trade, investment, and tourism activities. Airports also create new business and job opportunities for the surrounding community, thus contributing to improved public welfare (Akbar, 2023). Furthermore, the development of quality airport facilities is a crucial factor in supporting the increase in air transportation users and the development of the regional tourism sector (Ghifari, 2025).

One of the airports that plays a vital role in supporting regional development in West Nusa Tenggara Province is Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport, located in Central Lombok Regency. This airport serves as the main gateway for air transportation on Lombok Island and supports the development of leading tourist areas such as Mandalika and Gili Trawangan. The airport was built as a solution to the limited capacity of Selaparang Airport, which was no longer able to accommodate the increasing number of passengers and flight activity. Data shows that

the number of passengers arriving, departing, and transiting through Selaparang Airport continues to increase, reaching 676,889 arriving passengers, 701,664 departing passengers, and 148 transit passengers in 2010 (BPIW, 2012). Besides providing benefits for regional development, airport construction also has various social and economic impacts on surrounding communities. These impacts can include changes in land use, livelihoods, increased economic activity, and even changes in social interaction patterns. The presence of increasingly comprehensive transportation infrastructure can boost economic activity and accelerate regional development, but at the same time, it also has the potential to trigger social changes that require adaptation from local communities (Dumatubun, 2024).

Tanak Awu Village, Pujut District, Central Lombok Regency, is one of the areas directly impacted by the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport. Prior to the airport's construction, the majority of the community relied on dryland agriculture for their livelihoods. Pujut District itself boasts significant dryland agricultural potential, encompassing 16,549 hectares, or approximately 41.42% of the total dryland area in Central Lombok Regency (Central Lombok Regency Agriculture Office, 2020). However, this substantial agricultural potential has not yet fully translated into optimal well-being for the farming community (Pahlevi, 2019). The airport's presence has led to the emergence of new economic opportunities that have the potential to transform the livelihood structure and socioeconomic conditions of the community. Heads of households play a crucial role in household economic management and decision-making related to family welfare. Therefore, they are relevant informants for understanding the various social and economic changes resulting from the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport. Based on these conditions, this study aims to analyze the socioeconomic impact of the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport on heads of households in Tanak Awu Village, Central Lombok Regency.

Relevant Concepts and Theories

Social Change

Social change is a process of transformation that occurs in people's lives as a result of development and construction in a region. These changes can affect social structures, interaction patterns, values, norms, and how people view various aspects of life. According to Yuliza (2018), social change can be analyzed through three main indicators: changes in mindset, changes in behavior, and changes in community culture. Changes in mindset are characterized by increased public openness to developments in technology, and the importance of education in improving the quality of life. Meanwhile, changes in behavior are seen in the adjustment of people's activities and habits in daily life, both in the social and economic fields, in response to new conditions arising from development.

In addition to influencing mindsets and behavior, development can also drive cultural change within a society. Cultural change encompasses changes in values, norms, language, arts, and lifestyles that develop along with increased interaction between communities and the wider environment. Nevertheless, communities generally maintain local cultural values that are considered essential to their social identity. Therefore, indicators of changes in mindset, behavior, and cultural change can be used to understand how communities adapt to changes brought about by development and how these changes impact social life as a whole (Yuliza, 2018).

Economic Change

Economic change is a change that occurs in the structure and economic activities of a society as a result of the development process. Development often drives economic transformation from traditional sectors, such as agriculture, to more modern sectors, such as industry, trade, and services. According to Huda (2021), economic changes resulting from development can impact community welfare through the development of economic activity and the opening of various new business opportunities. In line with this, Suwarni (2016) explains that development causes a shift in people's livelihoods, from previously dependent on the agricultural sector to becoming more diverse with the development of the service and industrial sectors.

According to Carley in Ayuningtyas (2022), the economic impact of development can be measured through two main indicators: community income and employment opportunities. Community income is used to assess changes in economic conditions experienced by communities following development, whether they have increased or decreased. Meanwhile, employment opportunities are used to assess the extent to which development has created new job opportunities for the surrounding community. Increased income and increased employment opportunities indicate that development provides positive economic benefits, while limited access to employment can be a challenge that

arises in the development process. Therefore, these two indicators are important to use to assess the economic impact of development on community welfare.

Implementation Method

This study uses a qualitative approach to analyze the socio-economic impact of the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport on heads of families in Tanak Awu Hamlet, Tanak Awu Village, Central Lombok Regency. The informants in this study were 16 heads of families selected according to the research objectives. Data collection was conducted through in-depth interviews to obtain information on the social and economic changes experienced by the community after the airport construction. The data obtained were analyzed using the Miles and Huberman model of qualitative data analysis techniques which include the stages of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, as well as drawing conclusions and verification.

Results and Discussion

Social Impact

Changes in Mindset for Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport Development

Community Views Before the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport, the community still experienced differences of opinion between those who accepted and those who rejected it, especially regarding land acquisition. However, after the airport was operational, there was a significant change in views because the community began to feel its benefits, especially in improving the economy, transportation, and access to education. The presence of the airport was also seen as opening opportunities for the community to develop the future of their families, especially in the fields of education and employment opportunities outside the area. Over time, the mindset of the people of Tanak Awu Village became more open and began to be oriented towards the future of the next generation, including in aspects of education and cultural development. The following statement from informant 1, Mr. Aziz, as a community member of Tanak Awu I Hamlet on February 28, 2026, stated that:

"Before the construction of this airport, there was, as usual, a dispute between the landowners and the government. So, before construction began, there were some differences of opinion or differences between the development projects that took place there. At that time, some people accepted it, while others rejected it. Most of the people rejected it, especially those around Tanah Awu and Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport. Then, afterward, this airport in Lombok became very beneficial, because the economy around the airport improved, whether from economic growth through hotels or other travel, and transportation also experienced improvements.."

Table 1. Summary Results of Informant Indicators of Change in Mindset

Informant	Summary
Informant 1	Initially there was resistance to the construction of the airport, but after it was operational, he saw great benefits, especially in terms of economic improvement, ease of transportation, and educational and employment opportunities for the community.
Informant 2	Airports are important gateways for tourism and mobility, but changes in personal mindset are not very significant because they emphasize the accessibility aspect of the region.
Informant 3	Initially did not see the impact of development, but then realized the big changes especially in access to transportation, job opportunities, and the importance of children's education.
Informant 4	Initially thought the airport would not have a big impact, but then realized the economic improvement and the importance of education and openness to change.
Informant 5	Initially, they didn't really care, but then they saw the positive impact, especially on the economy and increasing awareness of family education.
Informant 6	Underestimating the impact of the airport, but later seeing new business opportunities and the importance of education for the family's future.
Informant 7	Was skeptical about the benefits of the airport, but then saw the increase in economic activity and started to think more about children's education.
Informant 8	Previously did not see a direct impact, but after seeing big changes in the surrounding area and began to focus on family education.
Informant 9	Thinking development was unimportant, but later realizing the benefits of better transportation and education.

Informant	Summary
Informant 10	Not paying attention to development, but then seeing the economic impact and the importance of children's education.
Informant 11	Didn't think there would be a big impact, but then realized the positive changes especially in the family's economy and education.
Informant 12	Initially not seeing a direct connection, but later becoming more optimistic about the future through education.
Informant 13	Didn't care, but then felt the economic changes and became more concerned about children's education.
Informant 14	Didn't expect much, but then realized the huge benefits the airport would have on economic and educational life.
Informant 15	Initially, they thought it would have no direct impact, but then they saw an increase in people's mobility and economy.
Informant 16	Initially considered a simple project, but then saw the real impact on the mobility and educational spirit of the family.

Based on the results, all respondents stated that the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport has brought positive changes to the community's mindset. Before construction, most people were indifferent or even doubted the airport's benefits. However, after its operation, the community began to feel a real impact, especially in terms of economic improvement, transportation access, and job opportunities. Furthermore, almost all respondents stated that the airport's presence has made them more concerned about their families' futures, particularly regarding their children's education. Informants are more motivated to send their children to higher education so they can compete in the increasingly open world of work. In terms of openness, the people of Tanak Awu Village are considered increasingly open to change. Their previously closed and traditional mindset has now begun to shift to a more modern, adaptive, and accepting mindset, while still maintaining local values.

Based on the research results, the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport had a significant impact on changing the mindset of the people of Tanak Awu Village. Before the airport's construction, most residents had a relatively traditional, passive mindset, and tended to be skeptical of the benefits of large-scale infrastructure development. They were more oriented towards local, subsistence economic activities, particularly in the agricultural sector. However, after the airport began operating, there was a significant shift in perception, as people began to recognize the tangible benefits of improved transportation access, regional openness, and new economic opportunities. This condition aligns with modernization theory, which explains that infrastructure development can be a major driver of social change, particularly in shaping a more rational, open, and progress-oriented mindset (Suryana, 2020).

This shift in mindset is also evident in the community's increasing focus on the future, particularly in children's education. Interview results indicate that almost all respondents are more motivated to send their children to higher education. This is driven by the awareness that regional development resulting from airport construction will increase competition in the job market, necessitating improvements in the quality of human resources. This phenomenon aligns with research by Prasetyo and Handayani (2021), which states that strategic infrastructure development not only impacts the economic aspect but also increases public awareness of education and encourages social mobility. Thus, the shift in community mindset is not limited to the economic aspect but also encompasses social and educational aspects.

Furthermore, change is also evident in the community's level of openness to modern developments. The people of Tanak Awu Village, who previously tended to maintain traditional lifestyles, are now showing a more adaptive attitude to social, economic, and technological changes. However, these changes do not eliminate the local values that have become part of the community's cultural identity. The community continues to uphold customary norms, religious values, and local traditions as part of their daily lives. This demonstrates that the social change that has occurred is selective, with the community able to adapt to modernization without losing their cultural identity. The construction of the airport is an external factor accelerating the process of social change, particularly in the aspect of community mindsets, which have become more open, dynamic, and progressive (Setiawan, 2022).

Nugroho's (2024) research also confirms that strategic infrastructure development in rural areas has a significant impact on transforming people's mindsets, particularly in increasing awareness of the importance of education, the creative economy, and involvement in modern economic activities. This demonstrates that

development not only impacts physical facilities but also drives fundamental changes in people's perspectives on life and the future.

It can be concluded that the airport development not only impacts the economy and infrastructure but also plays a significant role in shaping the mindset of the Tanak Awu Village community to become more progressive, open, and future-oriented. This change reflects a gradual process of social transformation, in which the community is able to adapt to environmental changes without abandoning deeply rooted local cultural values.

Changes in Behavior of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport Development

At the beginning of construction, the community was still not fully accepting the changes due to the construction process. However, after the airport was operational, there was an increase in economic activity that had an impact on changing community behavior to be more productive. The increase in social and economic activity of the community was marked by the development of businesses such as cafes, hotels, and trade businesses around the airport. However, not all residents experienced significant changes in employment, as the majority of people who work as farmers continued to maintain their jobs. This indicates that behavioral changes are more visible in the increase in additional economic activities, not a complete change in livelihood. The following is a statement from informant 1, Mr. Aziz, a resident of Tanak Awu I Hamlet on February 28, 2026, who stated that:

"Initially, our daily activities were still not very receptive, because of the development. But then our activities increased, there was economic growth, a lot of economic growth emerged, and incomes also increased. So it's very positive. Currently, the people of Tanah Awu are already feeling the positive effects. The economy is improving, unlike before. Now the economy has improved, there are many cafes, many hotels, and so on. Speaking about the habits of the people around the airport, it hasn't affected them. Some of us who live here, when we were farmers, have remained farmers, and indeed, people here have always farmed as well, and the surrounding area is also beautiful. But we, as farmers, still farm because we have land to cultivate. Whether it's planting rice, corn, and so on, and some of us even often grow watermelons."

Tabel 2. Summary Results of Informant Behavior Change Indicators

Informant	Summary
Informant 1	Community activity initially rejected the development, but after it was operational, economic activity increased and community income also rose.
Informant 2	There were no significant changes in the daily activities or socio-economic conditions of the community after the airport was built.
Informant 3	Social and economic activities increase and people interact more frequently and open new businesses.
Informant 4	Communities are becoming more productive with the emergence of new businesses and a shift to the service and trade sectors.
Informant 5	There are no major changes because some people still farm as before.
Informant 6	People are becoming more active and busy with increased economic activity.
Informant 7	There is a change in behavior due to job opportunities emerging around the airport.
Informant 8	Community activities become more dynamic and developing.
Informant 9	There has been an increase in economic activity, especially small businesses and trade.
Informant 10	People are becoming busier with economic and business activities.
Informant 11	People are more active in looking for new job and business opportunities.
Informant 12	People become more productive with increased economic activity.
Informant 13	People are more often active outside the home for work.
Informant 14	People become more active and productive in various activities.
Informant 15	Become more active and productive with new business opportunities.
Informant 16	Be more active in seeking additional work and work more productively.

Based on the overall results of the informants, the interviews revealed changes in community behavior following the airport's establishment, particularly in economic and employment activities. Most respondents stated that people have become more active, working outside the home more often, and taking advantage of economic opportunities emerging around the airport. Social and economic activity has also increased significantly. Many people have begun opening small businesses such as food stalls, transportation services, parking, boarding houses, and other trade businesses. This indicates a shift from traditional activities to service-based economic activities. However, several respondents also mentioned that some people still maintain traditional occupations, such as farming. Therefore, behavioral changes do not completely eliminate traditional occupations, but are adaptive and combinatory.

These behavioral changes are evident in the increased economic activity of the community, such as the emergence of small and medium-sized businesses around the airport. Many people have opened food stalls, transportation services, parking businesses, boarding houses, and various other forms of trade. This phenomenon demonstrates the diversification of livelihoods as a form of community adaptation to new economic opportunities arising from infrastructure development. This aligns with the theory of social change according to Structural Functionalism, which explains that changes in one part of the social system, such as infrastructure development, will affect other social structures, including employment patterns and economic behavior (Parsons in Widodo, 2021).

Furthermore, this increase in economic activity also indicates a process of modernization in community behavior, where people are becoming more productive, competitive, and oriented towards economic opportunities. According to research by Hidayat and Lestari (2022), the development of strategic infrastructure such as airports can create an economic multiplier effect that encourages local communities to develop new businesses and increase participation in the non-agricultural economic sector. Thus, changes in community behavior are not only individual but also impact the overall structure of the village economy.

However, these behavioral changes have not completely eliminated traditional livelihoods. Some people still maintain their jobs as farmers, although they have begun to combine them with new economic activities. This pattern indicates a combinatorial form of social adaptation, combining traditional and modern sectors simultaneously. This aligns with the findings of Sari and Wibowo (2023), who stated that rural communities affected by infrastructure development tend not to abandon the agricultural sector entirely, but rather to diversify their work to increase household income. Research by Nugroho (2024) also confirms that modern transportation infrastructure plays a crucial role in accelerating changes in rural economic behavior toward a service- and trade-based economy.

It can be concluded that airport development not only changes the economic conditions of the community but also shapes new behaviors that are more productive, adaptive, and oriented toward economic opportunities. However, these changes maintain a balance with traditional occupations, creating a hybrid pattern of economic behavior between the agricultural and service sectors.

Cultural Changes in Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport Development

The construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport did not eliminate the cultural values and customs of the Tanak Awu Village community. Local culture remains strongly preserved because the people of Central Lombok still maintain traditions passed down from generation to generation. The presence of immigrants has influenced social life, especially in interactions and differences in educational backgrounds, but has not changed the core culture of the community. Social norms and traditions are still preserved, including various arts and local wisdom that are still practiced today. Overall, the cultural changes that have occurred are adaptive, not changes that eliminate local cultural identity. The following is a statement from informant 1, Mr. Aziz, a member of the Tanak Awu I Hamlet community on February 28, 2026, who stated that:

"Because Central Lombok has such strong traditions, its values and culture are still preserved. In Central Lombok, it's in Sade Village. Sade is also known as a center for local wisdom, and its culture is still pristine. For example, some houses are lined with ready-to-use cow dung. You can see this on YouTube, TikTok, or Instagram for additional references. Furthermore, the cultural values here have not changed since the development began, just as they have been passed down from generation to generation. We still follow the culture."

Tabel 3. Summary Results of Informant Indicators of Cultural Change

Informant	Summary
Informant 1	Local culture remains strong and undisturbed, and traditions are preserved from generation to generation.
Informant 2	There is potential for foreign cultural influences, but the community still tries to maintain local cultural values.
Informant 3	Culture is still maintained but society is more open and selective towards outside culture.
Informant 4	The culture remains but has undergone adjustments, with the influence of immigrants on lifestyle.
Informant 5	Culture is still maintained, but there is social influence from immigrants.
Informant 6	There are changes to modern lifestyles but customs are still maintained.
Informant 7	Culture remains strong but is beginning to adapt to modern changes.
Informant 8	Culture remains intact but society is more open.
Informant 9	Culture is starting to experience changes in lifestyle but is still maintained.
Informant 10	Cultural changes occur but do not eliminate local identity.
Informant 11	Culture remains preserved but is starting to adapt to modernization.
Informant 12	Local culture is mixed with foreign culture but is still maintained.

Informant	Summary
Informant 13	Culture begins to mix with outside culture.
Informant 14	Culture remains strong and society remains open to new things.
Informant 15	Culture is maintained but is more adaptive to change.
Informant 16	Culture is still well maintained even though there are changes in the social environment.

Based on the overall results of the informants, it is clear that the cultural changes occurring in Tanak Awu Village are limited and do not eliminate local cultural values. Most respondents stated that customs remain strong and are maintained by the community. However, there have been changes in the increasingly modern lifestyle of the community, especially in terms of social interaction, dress, and language use. The presence of immigrants also has an impact in the form of openness, tolerance, and cultural exchange, although in some cases it has resulted in social adjustments. Social norms and community traditions are largely maintained, but their implementation has begun to undergo adjustments. Some traditions are said to be less frequently practiced due to the busy community and changes in modern lifestyles.

Based on the research results, the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport has had an impact on the cultural changes of the Tanak Awu Village community. However, these changes are selective and do not eliminate deeply rooted local cultural values. Interviews with informants indicate that local customs, religious values, and traditions are still maintained and preserved by the community as a social identity. This condition indicates that despite modernization due to infrastructure development, the community still has strong social control over the preservation of local culture. However, there have been changes in the increasingly modern lifestyles of society, particularly in social interaction patterns, dress, and language use. People are becoming more open to outside cultures brought by immigrants and the influence of high mobility around airport areas. Cultural change does not necessarily erase indigenous cultures; rather, it involves a process of blending and adapting local and foreign cultures (Koentjaraningrat in Putra, 2021).

The presence of immigrants around the airport area also contributes to increased community openness and tolerance. Increasingly intense social interactions lead to the exchange of cultural values and norms, making the community more adaptable to diversity. According to research by Haryanto and Sulastri (2022), the development of transportation infrastructure, such as airports, can create new spaces for social interaction, accelerating cultural diffusion and increasing community openness to social change. However, several informants stated that some local traditions are becoming less common. This is due to the increasing busyness of people in economic activities and changes in increasingly modern lifestyles. This condition indicates a shift in cultural functions from ritualistic to more flexible according to community needs. Research by Lestari (2023) explains that socioeconomic changes due to development can impact the sustainability of local traditions, especially if communities focus more on productive economic activities. Airport construction is a primary medium accelerating the influx of foreign cultural elements, but it does not completely replace local culture, but rather a selective and adaptive process (Nugroho, 2024).

Furthermore, the cultural changes that have occurred also demonstrate a balance between modernization and the preservation of local culture. The community still maintains traditional values such as mutual cooperation, religious activities, and certain social traditions, although their implementation has undergone adjustments to modern living conditions. This demonstrates that the people of Tanak Awu Village are able to adapt their culture without losing their local identity. It can be concluded that airport development does not eliminate local culture, but rather encourages selective, adaptive, and dynamic cultural transformation. This change reflects a process of integration between local and modern culture, occurring in balance amidst the community's socio-economic development.

Economic Impact

Income of Tanak Awu Village Community Due to the Impact of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport Construction

The construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport has had a positive impact on increasing community income. Before the airport, community income was relatively low, but after its operation there was a significant increase, from around Rp1,000,000–Rp1,500,000 to around Rp2,500,000–Rp3,000,000 per month. This increase in income came from various sectors such as jobs around the airport, small businesses, food stalls, boarding houses, and other service sectors. Thus, the presence of the airport is considered to have contributed significantly to improving the economic welfare of the Tanak Awu Village community. The following is a statement from informant 1, Mr. Aziz, a resident of Tanak Awu I Hamlet on February 28, 2026, who stated that:

"Initially, their income was low because there wasn't any development, but now that they're working there, their income has increased, unlike before. Previously, their income was modest, but now it's increased. There's been a change from just 1 million to 3 million. The presence of this airport can increase income, including income at the airport itself, income from sales, income from boarding houses, and income from restaurants. In short, the airport has improved the economy."

Tabel 4. Summary Results of Community Income Indicator Informants

Informant	Summary
Informant 1	Income increased significantly to around 3 million rupiah per month accompanied by new business opportunities.
Informant 2	There was no change in income before and after the airport was built.
Informant 3	Income increased from ±1.5 million to 2.5–3 million rupiah.
Informant 4	Income increased from ±1.8 million to around 3 million rupiah.
Informant 5	Income increased from ±1.2 million to 2.2 million rupiah.
Informant 6	Income increased from ±1.5 million to 2.8 million rupiah.
Informant 7	Income increased from ±1 million to 2.5–3 million rupiah.
Informant 8	Income increased from ±1.3 million to 2.5–3 million rupiah.
Informant 9	Income increased from ±1.6 million to 2.7 million rupiah.
Informant 10	Income increased from ±1.2 million to around 2 million rupiah.
Informant 11	Income increased from ±1.5 million to 2.8 million rupiah.
Informant 12	Income increased to around 2.5–3 million rupiah.
Informant 13	Income increased from ±1.4 million to 2.7 million rupiah.
Informant 14	Revenue increased due to business opportunities around the airport.
Informant 15	Income increased to more than 3 million rupiah.
Informant 16	Income increased due to additional service sector jobs.

Based on the overall results of the informants, the interview results showed that almost all respondents experienced an increase in income after the airport construction. Before the airport, the average community income was in the range of ± Rp1,000,000–Rp1,800,000 per month. After the airport, income increased to around ± Rp2,000,000 to more than Rp3,000,000 per month, especially for people who own businesses or work in the service sector around the airport. Sources of income have also diversified. While previously most people depended on the agricultural sector, after the airport, they began to earn additional income from stalls, trade, transportation, boarding houses, and work in the airport sector. Overall, the presence of the airport is considered to have contributed significantly to improving the economic welfare of the Tanak Awu Village community. Based on the research results, the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport has had a significant impact on increasing the income of the Tanak Awu Village community. The results of interviews with all informants showed that almost all respondents experienced an increase in income after the airport was built. Before the airport was built, the average community income was in the range of ±Rp1,000,000–Rp1,800,000 per month, which generally came from the agricultural sector and informal jobs. However, after the airport was operational, community income increased to around ±Rp2,000,000 to more than Rp3,000,000 per month, especially for people involved in the service and business sectors around the airport area.

This increase in income occurred not only in nominal terms, but also accompanied by changes in the structure of community income sources. While previously the community relied heavily on agriculture as its primary source of livelihood, the airport's presence has seen a diversification of livelihoods. People have begun developing new businesses such as food stalls, small businesses, transportation services, boarding houses, and working in both the formal and informal sectors related to airport activities. This situation indicates an economic transformation from the primary sector to a tertiary sector that is more oriented towards services and trade. This effect occurs due to the increased mobility of people and goods, which in turn creates new business opportunities and increases the income of the surrounding community (Todaro & Smith in Hidayat, 2021). Furthermore, research by Pratama and Suryani (2022) states that the presence of large-scale transportation infrastructure can increase household incomes in rural communities by expanding employment opportunities and fostering the growth of new economic sectors. In the context of Tanak Awu Village, this increase in income is also influenced by the community's ability to adapt to emerging economic opportunities around the airport. Communities with entrepreneurial initiatives tend to achieve higher income increases than those who rely solely on traditional sectors.

The increase in community income also reflects a more dynamic change in the village's economic structure. This demonstrates that airport development not only impacts infrastructure but also contributes directly to improving the community's economic well-being. According to Nugroho (2024), transportation infrastructure development plays a crucial role in improving the well-being of rural communities by creating new jobs and increasing local economic activity. It can be concluded that the airport's presence has significantly contributed to increasing the income of the Tanak Awu Village community. This change is not only quantitative in the form of increased income, but also qualitative in the form of diversified income sources, which has made the community's economic conditions more stable and sustainable.

Job Opportunities for the Tanak Awu Village Community Due to the Impact of the Construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport

The airport construction has opened up many new job opportunities for the people of Tanak Awu Village, particularly in the service, trade, transportation, and small business sectors. Furthermore, some family members have also found work or opened new businesses around the airport, such as traders and service workers. Although job opportunities are quite open, residents must still meet certain qualifications to be able to work at the airport. In general, job opportunities are considered sufficient for the local community, but still require certain abilities, skills, and requirements to be able to compete fairly. The following is a statement from informant 1, Mr. Aziz, a resident of Tanak Awu I Hamlet on February 28, 2026, who stated that:

"Yes, the airport opens up new job opportunities, so those living nearby work there. The airport also provides facilities for residents, provided they meet the qualifications and standards. As usual, their backgrounds are checked. Other requirements are also checked to ensure that those working at the airport are prepared and capable."

Tabel 5. Summary Results of Informant Job Opportunity Indicators

Informant	Summary
Informant 1	Airports open up new job opportunities but still require strict qualifications and selection.
Informant 2	Job opportunities exist but are not utilized by their families and access to information is still limited.
Informant 3	Many family members work in airport sectors such as cleaning, parking, and small businesses.
Informant 4	Job opportunities are open but are influenced by skills and social connections.
Informant 5	No family members work at the airport but job opportunities remain open.
Informant 6	The family opened a business around the airport.
Informant 7	There are family members working in the business sector around the airport.
Informant 8	There are family members working as parking attendants at the airport.
Informant 9	There are family members who opened small businesses around the airport.
Informant 10	The child works in a food stall near the airport.
Informant 11	The family works in the transportation and trade sectors.
Informant 12	Family members work in the transportation sector.
Informant 13	The family opened a small business around the airport.
Informant 14	No family members work at the airport.
Informant 15	Family members work in the trade sector around the airport.
Informant 16	Family members work in the service sector around the airport.

Based on the results, all respondents stated that the airport construction has opened new job opportunities for the surrounding community. These opportunities have emerged in various sectors such as transportation, security, cleaning, vendors, parking, and other small businesses. Some family members of respondents also gained employment or started new businesses due to the airport. This indicates a direct impact on increasing employment opportunities at the household level. However, regarding access to job opportunities, some respondents felt that these opportunities were not yet fully equitable. Frequently cited barriers included education, skills, job requirements, and competition from immigrants or outsiders. However, some respondents also believed that job access was already sufficiently open, requiring only increased outreach and skills development for the local community.

Based on the research results, the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Majid Airport has had a significant impact on increasing employment opportunities for the people of Tanak Awu Village. Interviews with all respondents indicated that the airport has opened up various new job opportunities in the service and trade sectors. These opportunities include transportation, security, cleaning, vendors, parking, and various small and medium-sized businesses located around the airport. This situation indicates an expansion of the local economic structure,

previously dominated by agriculture, to become more diverse and service-based. Furthermore, airport construction also has a direct impact on employment opportunities at the household level. Some respondents' family members reported finding new jobs or starting new businesses related to economic activity around the airport. This demonstrates the multiplier effect of infrastructure development, which not only creates formal jobs but also encourages the growth of the informal sector, absorbing local labor. This phenomenon aligns with regional economic theory, Labor Market Theory, which explains that increased investment and infrastructure development will increase labor demand across various economic sectors (Todaro & Smith in Hidayat, 2021).

However, the research also shows that access to these job opportunities is not fully equitable among the community. Some respondents stated that they face barriers to employment, caused by factors such as education level, skills, and job requirements set by companies or relevant agencies. Furthermore, competition with more highly qualified workers from outside the region has emerged. This indicates a gap in access to the job market, which remains a challenge for local communities. This situation aligns with research by Prasetyo and Nurhadi (2022), which states that large-scale infrastructure development is often accompanied by unequal access to employment, particularly if local communities lack the competencies needed for the modern labor market. In the context of Tanak Awu Village, this demonstrates that despite increased job opportunities, the community's adaptability is a crucial factor in determining the extent to which economic benefits are shared equitably.

On the other hand, respondents also believed that job opportunities are already quite open, but need to be supported by increased outreach, skills training, and empowerment of local communities to enable them to compete more effectively. According to Nugroho (2024), the success of infrastructure development in improving community welfare is largely determined by the readiness of human resources to capitalize on available economic opportunities. It can be concluded that the airport construction not only increases job opportunities in Tanak Awu Village but also encourages a transformation in the labor structure from the agricultural sector to the service sector. However, these benefits are still faced with challenges in the form of unequal access to jobs influenced by factors such as education, skills, and labor competition. Therefore, capacity building for the local community is crucial to ensure that existing job opportunities are enjoyed more equitably and sustainably.

Conclusion

The construction of Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport has had a significant social and economic impact on heads of families in Tanak Awu Village, Central Lombok Regency. From a social perspective, the airport's construction has led to a shift in the community's mindset, leading to a more open and future-oriented mindset. This shift in behavior is characterized by increased social and economic activity, and a selective cultural shift that continues without eliminating local customary values and traditions still maintained by the community. These changes demonstrate a process of community adaptation to the developments brought about by the airport's presence. From an economic perspective, the construction of Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport has had a positive impact on improving community welfare through increased income and the opening of new job opportunities. Furthermore, there has been a shift in community livelihoods from the agricultural sector to the service and trade sectors that are developing around the airport area. However, the utilization of these economic opportunities has not been fully equitable because it is still influenced by factors such as education, skills, and the level of labor competition. Overall, the airport's construction has made a positive contribution to social transformation and improving the economic conditions of the Tanak Awu Village community.

Suggestions for the Tanak Awu Village Government and the management of Zainuddin Abdul Madjid International Airport are that they need to improve community empowerment programs through skills training, improving access to education, and expanding employment opportunities for local residents so that the economic benefits of airport development can be felt more evenly. Furthermore, the community is expected to continue improving the quality of human resources and utilizing available economic opportunities without neglecting local cultural values. For future researchers, it is recommended to examine the impact of airport development from other aspects, such as the environment, social inequality, and long-term impacts on community welfare.

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